
Planning and Implementation of Universal Basic Education Programme in Cross River State: Implications for Effective Implementation

Ekpenyonganwan Godwin Anam

Department of Educational Management, Faculty of Education
University of Calabar, Calabar

Email: ekpenyonganwananam@gmail.com

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Abstract

The main purpose of this study was to investigate the planning and implementation of the Universal Basic Education programme in Cross River State. The study discussed the implications for effective implementation. Two research questions guided the study. A descriptive survey research design was adopted for the study. The population of the study consisted of all heads of public junior secondary schools; school administrators who are directly in charge of the programme implementation, school teachers and professional bodies' example the Nigerian Union of Teachers (NUT) in the state. A combination of stratified, proportional and judgemental sampling techniques was used in selecting a sample of 887 respondents. The instrument used for data collection was a questionnaire titled "Stakeholders Opinion Questionnaire on Implementation of UBE Programme (SOQIUP)". This was validated by three experts, two from Educational Management and one from Education Measurement and Evaluation in the faculty of education. A reliability estimate of 0.86 was obtained through the use of the Cronbach Alpha method. The collected data were analysed using mean, standard deviation and frequency counts. Findings indicated that the plan for the implementation of the Universal Basic Education Programme was done in a hurry, possibly without adequate consideration of necessities for its implementation in the state. The findings also revealed poor funding of education, lack of reliable statistics for planning and basic education not being free. It was, therefore, concluded that the low level of performance is associated with poor systematic needs assessment, hasty planning and implementation; hence, it was recommended that proper needs assessment be done regularly and continuously, as well as, strict adherence to the policy directives at the implementation stage.

Keywords: Effective, implementation, implication, planning, programme.

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Introduction

The major purpose of a social programme is to ameliorate some social problems or improve some social conditions. If the programme policy is sound and the programme plan is well implemented the expected social benefits should follow. However, those benefits are rarely certain. Practical and conceptual shortcomings combined with the intractable nature of other problems commonly undermine the effective implementation of such programmes, including education-related programmes (Rossi, Freeman & Lipsey, 1999). Managing the educational

industry in Nigeria vis-a-vis Cross River State according to Onyene 2005, NERDC (2008) requires highly conceptual, technical and critical planning through the use of veritable policy initiation, strategies and effective implementation mechanism. The educational system managers are also required to appreciate the importance of the inputs and processing mechanism and its implications on the outputs.

The Federal and State governments over the years have initiated several policy provisions aimed at achieving the goals of education for the overall development of the nation and individual states. The Universal Basic Education Programme (UBEP) was one of such provisions. The programme called 6-3-3-4 system has metamorphosed into the present 9-3-4 system christened 9 years Basic Education Programme. The 9-years Basic Education Programme which was formally launched on October 7, 2004, has three levels as follows: Lower Basic Education – from Primary 1-3; Middle Basic Education – from Primary 4-6; Upper Basic Education – from Junior Secondary 1-3 (Nigerian Educational Research and Development Council – NERDC, 2008). Although the UBE is a Federal Government initiative, its policy covers the 36 states and the Federal Capital Territory (FCT) Abuja. At the National Level the programme is managed by Universal Basic Education Commission (UBEC), at the state level it is controlled by State Universal Basic Education Boards (SUBEBs) and at the Local Government Areas, it is managed by the Local Government Education Authorities (LGEAs) (Ibhafidon & Osemuenkhae, 2018).

The programme is universal because it is open to all citizens regardless of sex, geographical location and physical status provided you are at that level – primary 1 to Junior Secondary 3. It is Basic because it is the foundation upon which all other levels of education are built and therefore, a requirement for human and national progress (F.M.E, 1998). The programme that was meant to be tuition-free, has as its goals to ensure basic numeracy, literacy and Lifelong skills; basic rudiments for creative thinking; high moral and ethical values; the spirit and yearning for entrepreneurship (NERDC, 2008). Since education, policies and programmes are dynamic, the UBE scheme must likewise be subjected to regular review of its planning and implementation and the assessment of its fulfilment of the intended target. However, the reverse appears to be the case as observed by NERDC (2008) and Okwori (2011) that Nigerians rely on emergency measures in planning and implementation of educational programmes. They attributed the collapse of erstwhile Universal Primary Education (UPE) 6-5-4 and UBE 6-3-3-4 programmes on hasty planning and implementation and asserted that these programmes approaches could not keep pace with the dynamics of social change and demands on education to meet emergency issues, global concern as well as addressing economic realities of the state. It was in the light of these shortcomings in the old systems, that the 9-year Basic Education was initiated to cater for the yearnings and aspirations of Nigerians with the resultant effect of fashioning education that is driven by the National Economic Empowerment and Development Strategy (NEEDS) (NERDC, 2003).

According to Okwori (2011), “planning means a rational and intelligent process of preparing or arranging a set of decisions for future activities directed at achieving goals and objectives by the best methods possible”. By this definition, planning implies giving thought

to the goals, aspirations and priorities of the people concerned. To plan well you are required to know the people's needs, goals, desires and aspirations. Okwori added that planning is not only concerned with objectives but goes further to include how to achieve the objectives. The aspect of how to achieve the objectives in planning is its implementation. Thus, programme planning and implementation are interrelated processes.

Despite the close relationship between planning and implementation, there exists a definite order in which planning comes before implementation. Nwadiani (1998), Gideon and Sorkaa (2008) and Gyang (2015) observed a management problem confronting the UBE programme in which implementation effort begins before planning. For instance, some politicians often make public pronouncements about educational programme implementation before planning or sometimes without a plan. This process disorder of "putting the cart before the horse" is always difficult to operate. Adesina in Akpotu (2014) defines educational planning as the process of applying scientific or rational procedures to the process of education growth and development to ensure the efficiency and effectiveness of the educational systems. There is a common adage that if you fail to plan, it means you plan to fail, many programmes fail to show impacts due to a fundamental problem of services delivery. Rossi, Freeman and Lipsey (1999) termed failure to deliver programme interventions specified in the plan as implementation failure. They identified three kinds of implementation failures: First, no intervention, or not enough is delivered; second, the wrong intervention is delivered; third, the intervention is unstandardized. World Bank (2008) observed that the UBE sector of the Ministry of Education was characterised by poor planning and budgeting, weak financial management and procurement practices. Others included corruption and poor management of available resources.

Omotere (2011) carried out a study aimed at examining the problems of UBE programme implementation in Ijebu-ode Local Government Area (LGA) of Ogun State, Nigeria. A population of 2,354 teachers and a sample of 230 was used for the study, questionnaire instrument was used to collect data which were analysed using simple percentages. It was observed in the study that poor supervision and monitoring of schools, inadequate infrastructural facilities, working distance to school, and lack of qualified teachers among other factors were responsible for poor UBE programme implementation in the area. Regular supervision and monitoring of schools were recommended. This finding was supported by later studies (Ambe, Agbor & Eyo, 2018; Ayara, Essia & Udah, 2013). For instance, Ambe et al. (2018) observed that with the teachers and the best curriculum in a school without basic infrastructure such as adequate classrooms, benches and office space, the implementation of the curriculum will not be effective and the objectives will fall short of being implemented. A study conducted in Cross River State aimed at examining the influence of the provision of UBE facilities on the level of classroom control. Ayara et al. (2013) adopted the survey design method and sampled 1,242 educational institutions, both private and public primary and secondary schools). They noted that Cross River State has completely renovated 60 secondary schools building to ease accommodation problems, but concluded that there is still a huge gap in the number of desks available per school and student in the state.

Opo, Odey and Nkanu (2018) conducted a study to ascertain the adequacy of government funding towards the successful implementation of the UBE scheme in Cross River State between the years 2010-2015. The study adopted a descriptive research design method to tackle the problem, using all the 18 LGAs of the state. One research question was posed and answered using frequency counts and simple percentages to analyse the responses of 297 respondents used. In addition, the results were summarised in a table and a bar chart. It was concluded in the study that the management of the UBE programme and the Cross River State government did not consider education as a priority as they could not access a large (chunk) of the fund (grant) meant for its functionality. Thus, glaring issues such as poor management, lack of provision of teaching materials, poor condition of service, among other issues hindered the successful implementation of the UBE programme in the state. According to Akpotu (2014) the problems of educational planning and implementation in Cross River State could be summarised as follows: Doing the first thing last (process disorder); poor systematic needs assessment, lack of accurate data; inadequate resources; planners are often different from those implementing programmes; distressing economy; political instability, and so on. More often than not, educational plans are hardly effectively implemented and are not periodically and continuously monitored and evaluated to identified lapses. These and some other issues not mentioned here make planning and implementation efforts in the UBE programme inefficient and ineffective. In a multi-ethnic and multi-professional society as Cross River State, a situation where due process is not followed and where programme design is hastily implemented without adequate articulation of the basic requirements is unacceptable and should not be encouraged. The rural population of women are mostly illiterate against 14 per cent of males in urban areas (Psacharopoulos, 2014). These rural-urban and sex disparities should also not be allowed to persist.

Statement of the problem

The major problem of the 9- year universal basic education programme in Cross River State is a management issue in which planning and implementation processes are disorderly and hastily executed. A situation where reservations or outright condemnations are expressed in different quarters about the use of the scheme to advance the state educational prosperity. This situation leads to a state-wide problem that requires appropriate attention. It is an attempt to meet up with these mounting challenges and also be able to forecast future programme needs, that this study was undertaken to examine the opinion of stakeholders about the implementation level of the 9-year UBE programme in Cross River State.

Research questions

The following research questions are posed to guide data collection and analysis.

1. What is the general opinion of stakeholders on the implementation level of the 9-year Basic Education Programme in Cross River State?
2. What are the observed lapses in the implementation, of the 9-year Basic Education programme in the state?

Methods

The study examined the implementation level of the 9-year UBE programme in Cross River State, Nigeria. It is a descriptive survey design involving major stakeholders in education across the 18 LGA of the state. These stakeholders include All heads of public junior secondary schools; school administrators who are directly in charge of the programme implementation. School teachers and professional bodies' example the Nigerian Union of Teachers (NUT). These groups constitute the target population for the study. The sample was chosen from different sampling units through multiple sampling procedures as shown in Table 1. In all, a total of 887 respondents formed the study's sample. The teachers were selected unevenly across the senatorial districts and local government areas. Thus, a combination of stratified, proportional and judgemental sampling techniques was applied. This was done to ensure fair representation of the target population.

Table 1: The sample sampling unit and sampling procedures

S/N	Sample unit	No in population	No per LGA	Total sample	Sampling proceeded
1	Heads of junior secondary school	264	-	264	Wholistic
2	Chairman of SUBEB	1	-	-	Wholistic
3	Heads of LGEAs	18	1	18	Wholistic
4	Junior school teachers	5,778	10%	578	Proportional
5	Teachers' association (LG chapters')		2	26	Judgemental
	Total			887	

A well-structured questionnaire christened Stakeholders Opinion Questionnaire on Implementation of UBE Programme (SOQIUP) in Cross River State was used for data collection from respondents. The instrument has different sections: Section 1 contains demographic information such as position/post, location, subject area, many subjects taught etc. section II contains eight items on stakeholders' opinion on the level of the implementation. Each item has four-point response options – Strongly Agree (SA)-4; Agree (A)-3; Disagree (D)-2 and Strongly Disagree (SD)-1. Section III consists of implementation lapses; a lapse is a departure from what is necessary. It is used here as the necessities that are missing in the implementation process. The lapses are categorised as government-related and school-related. A further grouping, of the lapses, are High prevalence and low prevalence. If the lapses occurred in at best 50 per cent of the LGAs, they are grouped as high prevalence and below 50 per cent are considered low prevalence. All together 13 lapses were identified and used. The drafted instrument was subjected to face and content validation by two experts in the Departments of Educational Management and one expert in Educational Measurement and Evaluation. It was later trial tested in Akwa Ibom state JSS schools for its reliability. A reliability estimate of 0.86 was obtained through the use of the Cronbach Alpha method. The index was considered high enough for use. Local government area codes were included for ease of analysis.

Results and Discussion

This section deals with the results of the statistical analysis of data for the study as well as their interpretation and discussions. Mean (\bar{x}), standard deviation (S) and frequency counts (F) were used in analysing the data based on the research questions guiding the study.

Research question 1

What is the general opinion of stakeholders on the level of implementation of the 9-year Basic Education programme in Cross River State? To answer the research question which sought empirical information from major stakeholders on their opinion on the extent of implementation of the 9-year Universal Basic Education scheme in the state, respondents were requested to provide their responses by ticking the options (SA to SD) after items 1-8 as shown in Table 2.

Table 2: Frequency, mean scores and standard deviations of responses to items on the implementation of the 9-year UBE scheme

s/n	Statement	SA	A	D	SD	\bar{x}	S	Decision
1	The planning for the implementation of a 9-year UBE is not in a hurry	20	98	298	481	1.6	0.81	Not accepted
2	The 9-year Basic education is not a solution to the states' problems	160	182	281	264	2.7	0.83	Accepted
3	Education and training facilities have continually expanded in response to special needs.	34	300	316	237	2.1	0.86	Not accepted
4	French is being taught as a compulsory subject in all JSS classes in the state.	20	36	340	491	1.5	0.90	Not accepted
5	Every child in JSS classes learns at least one of the three major Nigerian languages	41	82	204	560	1.6	0.87	Not accepted
6	ICT is now emphasised at all levels of JSS classes	62	209	300	316	2.0	0.81	Not accepted
7	Adequate strategies were not being mapped out before the implementation of the 9-year UBE	148	240	398	221	3.7	0.86	Accepted
8	The 9-year UBE programme implementation is location-sensitive	264	261	198	164	2.7	0.81	Accepted
	Average					2.24	0.82	Not accepted

Note: Questionnaire items were adopted from Obioma, Nafo, Salva, Otagosan and Omole (2008).

As a decision rule of thumb, an item that attracts a mean rating score of below 2.5 is considered not accepted. Item by item interpretation and discussion of the results shown in Table 2 are as follows: Item one with a mean score (\bar{x}) of 1.6 and standard deviation (S) of 0.81 attracts a 'not accepted' remark. It is interpreted to mean that the plan for the implementation of the 9-year Basic Education programme was done in a hurry possibly without adequate consideration of necessities for its implementation in the state. It might also be possible that the politicians were in a hurry to score a political goal not minding the consequences of hasty

actions. This finding conforms with the findings by Gideon and Sorkaa (2008) and Gyang (2015) who found that poor planning caused by a hasty attitude leads to the unsuccessful implementation of the UBE programme in Nigeria.

The mean score (\bar{x}) and standard deviation (S) of item two are 2.7 and 0.83 respectively and its remark is “accepted”. It is interpreted to mean that the 9-year Basic Education programme is not a solution to the state problems. This position of the stakeholders could be a result of the programme inability to attain its full mandate as certain prerequisites were not considered for effective implementation. Moreover, as noted earlier in this study, the 9-year Basic Education which was meant to be free and compulsory, stakeholders provided oral and informal information that all categories of fees were being collected from students depriving some less privileged ones of schooling.

Item 3: It has a mean score (\bar{x}) of 2.1 and a standard deviation (S) of 0.86. The result is interpreted to mean that education and training facilities do not expand in response to societal needs. This finding corroborates earlier research findings by Opoh, Odey and Nkanu (2018) and Akpotu (2014) who identified poor systematic needs assessment as a problem of UBE programme implementation. The implementation failures experienced in the 9 years Basic Education System could probably emanate from a failure to deliver enough intervention.

Items 4, 5 and 6 attracted a decision of ‘Not Accepted’ following their respective rating scores $\bar{x} = 1.5$, S = 0.90; $\bar{x} = 1.6$, S = 0.87 and $\bar{x} = 2.0$, S = 0.81. Item 4 interpretation is that the French language is not being taught in all JSS classes across the state, item 5 result reveals that not every child in JSS classes learns at least one of the three major Nigerian languages of Igbo, Yoruba and Hausa; and item 6 result reveals that ICT is not emphasized at all levels of JSS classes. The three provisions, items 4, 5 and 6, exist in theory most probably as a result of the dearth of teachers for these subjects. Facilities for effective utilization of ICT in school are also lacking in some schools as noted earlier. These findings confirm with the findings of Obiom et al (2008), Omotere (2011) and World Bank (2008), who asserted that inadequate facilities, lack of qualified teachers etc accounted for poor UBE programme implementation in Nigeria.

Item 7 has a rating score of $\bar{x} = 3.7$ with S = 0.86 and attracts an acceptance remark. The respondents opined those adequate strategies were not being put in place before the implementation of the programme. It could be the policymakers (politicians) might have made some careless policy statements without considering their implementation for implementation, thereby implementing before planning as observed by Gyang (2015).

The result of item eight (8) indicates a mean score (\bar{x}) of 2.7 and a standard deviation (S) of 0.81 meaning the remark is accepted and that the 9-year UBE programme implementation is sensitive to location. Stakeholders' opinion was high that there is a clear disparity between the urban and rural schools in the implementation of the UBE programme in the state. Most of the schools in the rural areas lack French teachers, have no teachers in the three major Nigerian Languages; have no ICT teachers and have a general shortage of teachers in other disciplines.

Whereas urban schools are relatively favoured in having teaching and non-teaching staff, there is therefore poor UBE programme implementation, particularly in the rural area schools. This finding is in agreement with the assertion by Rossi, Freeman and Lipsey (1999) that implementation failure occurs as a result of no adequate intervention delivery.

A close observation of the results displayed in Table 2 shows that all the eight items under investigation receive negative responses from respondents. Similarly, the overall or mean the aggregate of 2.23 and standard deviation of 0.82 is obtained indicating that the implementation of the 9-year Basic Education Programme in Cross River State has a low-level status. The low-level performance of the programme could be traced to factors such as inadequate facilities, poor managerial skills and lack of foresight by policymakers.

Research questions 2

What are the observed lapses in the implementation of the 9-year Basic Education Programme in Cross River State? As indicated earlier the lapses are grouped into Government and School-related. Lapses that occur in at least 50% of the LGAs are considered high prevalence and Lapses that occur in fewer than 50% of LGAs are grouped low prevalence. Local Government Areas and their number codes are indicated for ease of identification and discussion as shown in Table 4. Table 3 however, presents the identifying code for each LGA to serve as a key to understanding Table 4.

Table 3: Local Government Areas and their codes

LGA	Code	LGA	Code	LGA	Code	LGA	Code
Abi	01	Biase	06	Ikom	11	Ogoja	16
Akamkpa	02	Boki	07	Obanliku	12	Yakurr	17
Akpabuyo	03	Calabar Municipal	08	Obubra	13	Yala	18
Bakassi	04	Calabar South	09	Obudu	14		
Bekwara	05	Etung	10	Odukpani	15		

A close look at Table 4 reveals that poor funding of education, lack of reliable statistics for planning, basic education not being free, and dearth of Nigerian languages' teachers affect all Local government areas and they top the list of high prevalence lapses with 100 per cent. These are closely followed by poor supervision and monitoring, dearth of technical teachers, poor infrastructural facilities in schools, and delay in execution of the project with all local government areas affected except Calabar Municipality and Calabar South Local Government Areas. They are also high prevalence lapses with 89 per cent of the Local government areas Calabar Municipality and Calabar south appear exempted from almost all the lapses as a result of their metropolitan status, and the seat of the state government. This confirms the earlier observation that the programme implementation is sensitive to location (Psacharopoulos, 2014).

Also in the list of high prevalence lapses are teachers' poor attitude to work and poor continuous assessment practices with 78 per cent; and much emphasis on theory at implementation stage as well as inadequate instructional materials with 72 per cent. Large classes in schools in a lapse that appears in Calabar municipality (08) and Calabar South (09)

Local Government Areas and has a low prevalence status of 11 per cent. In Cross River State all the Local Government Areas headquarters have urban status except Etung Local Government Areas (10), and the data obtained from these headquarters have a high tendency of low prevalence lapses. However, the high prevalence lapses from their surrounding rural communities have overriding effects and therefore subsume their status as rural areas. The implementation of the 9-year UBE programme in the state suffering many lapses thereby earning a low level of success.

Table 4: Level of Prevalence and percentage distribution of lapses in the implementation of 9-year UBE programme by LGAs

S/N	Lapses: Government-related	LGAs affected	%	Low/High
1	Lack of reliable statistics for planning.	All LGAs	100	H
2	Poor funding of Education	All LGAs	100	H
3	Basic Education is not free	All LGAs	100	H
4	A dearth of Nigerian Languages teachers	All LGAs	100	H
5	Poor supervision and monitoring	All LGAs except 08 & 09.	89	H
6	A dearth of technical teachers	All LGAs except 08 & 09.	89	H
7	Poor infrastructural facilities in schools.	All LGAs except 08 & 09.	89	H
8	Delay in execution of projects.	All LGAs except 08 & 09.	89	H
9	Much emphasis on theory at the implementation stage	All LGAs except: 08, 09, 11, 16 & 17	72	H
10	Inadequate instructional materials school-related	All LGAs except: 08, 09, 11, 16 & 17	72	H
11	Lapses: School-related Teachers' poor attitude to work.	All LGAs except: 08, 09, 16 & 17	78	H
12	Poor continuous assessment practice.	All LGAs except: 08, 09, 11 & 17	78	H
13	Large classes in schools	Only 08 and 09	11	L

Conclusion/Recommendation

The 9-year Basic Education programme in Cross River State has a low level of implementation status. The basic principles of NEEDS underlying the basic education scheme have not been realised rather at operating at the implementation stage are mere theories, from the statistical perspective. The low level of performance is associated with failure to deliver enough intervention, poor systematic needs assessment, hasty planning and implementation. Therefore, this paper recommends that there should be proper needs assessment to be done regularly and continuously. School supervision and monitoring should be conducted with utmost sincerity by school administrators. There should be strict adherence to the policy directives at the implementation stage. Above all government should make education a priority by adequately funding it.

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